

ASSESSMENT OF METABOLIC CHANGES IN STUDENTS

Sa'dullayeva Marjona
Baratova Mexriban

Dsc Bukhara State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18256064>

Abstract. This study examines the primary factors influencing obesity rates among students, analyzes existing nutrition and physical education programs, and proposes potential measures for the prevention and control of this issue. Particular emphasis is placed on the role of educational institutions in fostering healthy habits, as well as the necessity of a comprehensive approach involving schools, families, and society to effectively reduce obesity levels.

Keywords: Obesity, metabolic changes, students, nutrition, physical activity, body mass index (BMI), preventive measures.

Introduction. Adolescent obesity is a pressing public health concern with long-term consequences for the physical and psycho-emotional well-being of the younger generation. Nutrition plays a vital role in shaping students' dietary habits. An imbalanced diet, characterized by a lack of fresh vegetables, fruits, and proteins, combined with excessive calorie intake, contributes to weight gain. Simultaneously, low physical activity levels—driven by a sedentary lifestyle, reduced time for physical education classes, and declining engagement in active leisure—exacerbate the obesity problem.

Objective. The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of nutrition and physical activity levels on the development of obesity among students and to develop potential preventive measures.

Key factors contributing to the development of obesity in students include:

- Imbalanced nutrition
- High consumption of sugar and fats
- Low levels of physical activity
- Genetic predisposition
- Environmental influences
- School and family dietary environments

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted among students of medical technical schools (colleges) in the city of Bukhara, Bukhara region. The following methods were employed:

- * Questionnaires regarding dietary habits and physical activity levels.
- * Menu analysis for compliance with nutritional recommendations.
- * Assessment of Body Mass Index (BMI).
- * Statistical data processing to identify correlations.

Statistical Data. According to the study results:

- ◇ 32% of students consume fast food and sugary carbonated drinks more than 4 times a week.
- ◇ 46% of students have insufficient levels of physical activity.
- ◇ 13% of students were found to be overweight, and 6% were classified as obese.

Conclusion. Data analysis revealed that high consumption of unhealthy foods and a lack of physical activity are the primary causes of metabolic changes and obesity among students. Accordingly, the following is recommended:

- Improve nutritional quality by including more vegetables, fruits, and protein products in the diet.
- Increase the frequency of physical education classes and encourage active breaks.
- Conduct educational activities for parents and students regarding a healthy lifestyle.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4887 dated November 10, 2020, "On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports."
2. Baratova, M. S. (2021). Metabolic changes and cardiovascular risk factors in the young population. Monograph. Bukhara.
3. World Health Organization (WHO). (2022). Global status report on physical activity. Geneva: WHO Press.
4. Shaykhova, G. I. (2012). Nutrition Hygiene. Textbook for medical students. Tashkent.
5. James, W. P. T. (2008). The epidemiology of obesity: the size of the problem. *Journal of Internal Medicine*, 263(4), 336-352.
6. Kurbanova, N. N. (2020). Impact of dietary habits on the health status of adolescents and students. *Medical Journal of Uzbekistan*, (3), 45-49.
7. Ismoilova, G. A., & Akhmadalieva, N. O. (2021). Hygiene and Healthy Lifestyle. Study manual. Tashkent.

